

LEGAL SCIENCE AND EDUCATION: PROBLEMS, METHODOLOGY, SOLUTIONS

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Annotation: The article deals with the problems of legal reality, actual problems of legal theory and practice, legal education and an approaches to their solutions

Key words: professional competence, legal literacy, methodology, legal science, low enforcement practice, modernization of education

The problem of finding modern approaches is common to legal science and education, since they are interrelated. The interdependence of legal science and education is obvious: law universities/faculties train personnel not only for practical activities, but also for scientific ones; science, in turn, developing, determines the modification of curricula, changes in the directions and methods of training specialists. Science and education are important components of society, determining its present and future reality. The development and prosperity of society (social progress) is possible provided that they are based on ensuring peace, respect and protection of human rights, democracy and the rule of law. The transition period in any country is naturally associated with active reform of all spheres of society. And this is a special stage in the development of the state and law, which determines the goals and objectives of legal science and education.

The legal theoretical field and the practice of law enforcement in real life do not always coincide, but this is quite normal. As the philosopher Merab Mamardashvili accurately noted, a person is doomed to be crucified between ideal and reality. The desire to achieve an ideal "launches" the development process. This is true both for legal science and the training of lawyers.

Modern legal science is characterized by greater freedom of creative search, plurality of views, and the possibility of sound criticism of existing gaps. At the same time, legal science, like education, is forced to respond to the challenges of the new (turbulent) reality - the rapid development of society, globalization, digitalization, expansion and intensification of communications on the Internet and in all spheres of human life and society, the constant complication of legal relations, variability and the dynamism of legal reality. In this regard, one of the pressing problems of scientific research in legal science of the modern period is the issues of methodology and its role. It should be noted that when developing a methodology, legal science faces certain difficulties, which are caused by the need to find clear guidelines for state-legal construction, as well as general crisis phenomena in the humanities at the turn of the 20th-21st centuries. Legal science, due to the vast amount of empirical material accumulated, is faced with very specific tasks of improving legal technology, optimizing the legislative process and law enforcement practice, systematizing and codifying legislation. Legal science and education of the modern period are clearly practice-oriented in nature. She is expected to provide specific methods for solving various issues in the legal field. Modern

legal knowledge in the post-Soviet space is becoming more and more detailed due to the increased volume of legislation and its sectoral specification.[3]

There are many problems in the legal field that are waiting to be resolved. We can highlight the following: legal uncertainty - lack of clarity and unambiguity in legislation, which is typical for the reform stage; accessibility of justice – lack of equal access to judicial protection; the use of outdated laws - the use of laws that do not correspond to modern realities, which is due to the lag of theory from the increasingly complex reality; insufficient protection of citizens' rights - lack of effective protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens; disproportionate punishment - the use of too harsh or lenient punishment; insufficient efficiency of the legal system - lack of efficiency and effectiveness in law enforcement activities, which impedes the development of society; Legal corruption is the abuse of official position in the legal system. Solving a number of problems is possible by increasing the level of professional competence of a lawyer, which, as a system, consists of: legal literacy, information, communication, moral and ethical, organizational, intellectual, pedagogical. The professionalism of a lawyer can be understood as a set of positive professional competencies; only in such a combination will we obtain a highly qualified specialist in legal sciences and jurisprudence. [2] The following competencies are necessary for a lawyer to be successful in his professional activities, according to analysts and employers:

-hardskills are professional knowledge and skills. Thus, a lawyer receives specialized knowledge at a university and increases it in the process of work. This group of skills includes knowledge of legislation and the ability to apply it in practice, knowledge of foreign languages, etc.

- softskills - flexible skills that are associated with the personality of the person himself, his individual qualities. These include, in particular, creativity, communication skills, negotiation skills, etc.

A lawyer should have: 1. good knowledge of the main branches of law and legal procedures; 2. deep knowledge in a certain area of jurisprudence; 3. ability to solve complex problems (critical thinking); 4. ability to work with large volumes of data; 5. good command of a foreign language (primarily English); 6. Oratory and public speaking skills; 7. interaction skills and ability to work in a team; 8. ability to manage time (timemanagement); 9. ability to negotiate; 10. good skills in the field of information technology.[5]

It should be noted that for the development of critical thinking, both legal theorists and practitioners, for their intellectual literacy, for the development of oratory skills, and scientific creativity, the study of formal logic is very important. Unfortunately, in university curricula, the course volume (number of hours) tends to be reduced, which is unlawful. The development of a culture of thinking - clarity, accuracy, evidence, flexibility, criticality, systematicity - is impossible without studying logic. Today, with the accelerating digitalization of public life, cybercrime is actively developing, which seems to be ahead of legislative activity, which determines the need to develop predictive thinking among both legal scholars and practitioners. It is clear that laws cannot change every day and cover all possible real cases of crimes, but being able to anticipate trends and predict the need for certain laws in advance is necessary and important. At the same time, significant indicators of the competitiveness and professional maturity of a specialist today are the ability, desire and readiness not only to carry out professional activities in standard areas and volumes, but also

to implement innovative solutions to new professional tasks of our time, which are characterized by uncertainty in the initial conditions and in the formulation of the tasks, redundancy or deficiency of information and resources, contradictions that require resolution, ambiguity, variability of permitted solutions, the presence of risk in the implementation of results. The labor market requires lawyers who are able to act clearly, quickly and efficiently, and most importantly, to independently make decisions in a problematic professional and legal field. The main criterion for the competence and professionalism of a young lawyer is the ability to quickly find effective solutions to problems arising in legal practice.

In the conditions of democratization of society and the strengthening of individual principles, the role and nature of the legal profession have fundamentally changed: it has become of a clearly public nature. In these conditions, a lawyer has the opportunity to directly influence the improvement of the legal culture of subjects of legal behavior, to ensure the implementation of individual rights and freedoms through the institutions of the national legal system, civil society institutions, and international mechanisms. To do this, a lawyer requires professional competencies developed in the practical part (that is, in terms of skills). They are necessary so that a lawyer can serve to promote progressive legal ideas, develop solutions to various professional problems arising in a multipolar world, in a variable and dynamic legal reality, and, in fact, for the successful development of the lawyer's career. The current stage of development of society and the requirements of society for the competencies of lawyers make the study and formation of practical skills in future professionals urgently necessary.[4]

The formation of a rule of law state in Uzbekistan (Russia and other countries of the post-Soviet space), its formation as an organic part of the world community, is absolutely impossible without the presence of highly educated legal specialists capable of effective professional activity. The level of their training must correspond to the needs of the country's development and modern demands of the labor market. The modernization and development of higher legal education must be proactive and continuous. [1, P.330-333] Legal science, using modern approaches, can contribute to the modernization of education. The prospects for the development of legal science, as well as education, can be assessed quite positively. Legal knowledge in the post-Soviet space as a whole, having adopted the methodological and empirical experience of the past, as well as incorporating the best developments of world jurisprudence, is capable of constructively updating the further growth of scientific potential in the field of jurisprudence.

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